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Public evaluation Report

Results of Open Call (COESO-CALL-2021) for recipients of financial support

Project **acronym:** COESO

Project **grant agreement number:** No. 101006325

Project **full name:** Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues

The **COESO project** (Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues) funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101006325, launched an Open Call (COESO-CALL-2021) to **fund 5 pilot projects** to implement innovative Citizen Science projects in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), inviting civil society and researchers to apply.

Call information

The call was published on the COESO project [website](#) and on the Horizon 2020 Participants Portal – [opportunities competitive calls](#) (on November, 30th 2021). Full call details were available [here](#).

The Open call was also published and disseminated on the CRIA [website](#).

The Open call application and selection process had **two rounds**:

The 1st round – call for Short Proposals – started on November, 30th 2021 and closed on 31st of January 2022 (17:00 CET).

In the first-round applicants were invited to submit a Short Proposal containing a brief description of the project purpose, objectives, team and budget.

Applicants were informed about the submission process and were required to send the Short Proposal and all the required documents by e-mail (by 30th January 2022, 17:00 CET).

An **Info Session** was carried out to potential participants interested in submitting proposals to the Open Call. Around 100 participants attended our live information session webinar on December 14th, 2021 (12:00-13:00 CET), where it provided an overview of the COESO project, outlined the eligibility requirements and all the application procedures and answered questions from the potential applicants.

A total of **172 proposals** were received for this round.

Response to the Call in detail

	Number of proposals
Proposals received (1st round)	172
Proposals received within deadline	137
Eligible proposals (for evaluation)	93
Proposals above threshold	27
Selected proposals to 2 nd round	27

The evaluation and selection process has been completed. All the applicants have been informed about the results, notified by email (on February 25th, 2022). Applications evaluated by the jury also received an “Individual evaluation report” (on February 25th, 2022).

The 2nd round – call for Full Project Proposals – started on March, 2nd and closed on the 31st of March 2022 (17:00 CET).

Successful applicants selected in the first-round (27) were invited to submit a Full Project Proposal within the second-round.

Applicants were informed about the submission process and were required to send the Full Project Proposal and all the required documents by e-mail (by 31st March 2022, 17:00 CET).

The selected applicants were also invited to attend a Mentoring Workshop (online, on March 2nd, 2022), where several COESO partners outlined the COESO project — specifically the roles and responsibilities that the pilot projects have within it — and answered questions from the participants.

A total of **25 proposals** were received for this round.

Response to the Call in detail

	Number of proposals
Proposals received (2nd round)	25
Proposals received within deadline	24
Eligible proposals (for evaluation)	18
Selected proposals	5

The evaluation and selection process has been completed.

The final selection meeting with the top 10 highest evaluations was organized with the participation of elements of the COESO team and of the COESO Advisory Board. From this meeting emerged the 5 projects best ranked to receive funding.

All the applicants have been informed about the results, notified by email (on April 22nd, 2022) and have received the ranking list (2nd round). Applications evaluated by the jury also received an “Individual evaluation report” (on April 22nd, 2022).

The top 5 applications were informed of the results and of the selection of their proposals to receive financial support.

The **5 selected proposals** will receive funding for a total amount of **248.443,00 EUR**.

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List of selected proposals

Pilot title and acronym	Organization	Country	Funding awarded
Playful Futures: sci-fi online LARP ethnography for Mediterranean coastal communities	Edgeryders OÜ	Estonia	49.712,00
	Techno-Anthropology Lab (TANTLab) - University of Aalborg	Denmark	EUR
	Culture Hub Croatia (CHC)	Croatia	
DiMDiCi: Digital Mapping with Disabled Citizens	Hochschule für Gesundheit Department of Community Health (HS Gesundheit)	Germany	48.731,00
	University of Twente, Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation (UT-ITC)	The Netherlands	EUR
LUNCH-BOX-MONITOR -Insight into the nutritional quality of school lunch-boxes to assess food insecurity among primary school children	Ghent University Let Us Rikolto Belgium Flemish Institute of Healthy Living	Belgium	50.000,00 EUR
Women for Water (WfW): Mapping water quality from the river to the glass	University of Antwerp, Institute of Development Policy (IOB)	Belgium	50.000,00 EUR
	Aqua-Farms Organization (AFO)	Tanzania	
AGORAge: Ageing in a Caring Community	Rovira i Virgili University - URV	Spain	50.000,00 EUR
	ISRAA- Istituto per Servizi di Ricovero e Assistenza agli Anziani	Italy	

